

Economic Development and Human Development

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Abstract: If we observed, the basic purpose of development is to enlarge people's choices. It concern with the sustainable improvement in the quality of life for all people. The raising per capita income and consumption is part of the purpose of development but reducing poverty, expanding access to health services and increasing educational levels are also important, meeting these goals requires a comprehensive approach of development. So the human development approach is rediscovery in the area of economic development. The present paper is trying to find the concept of human development which has relates with the country's economic development. The concept of economic development has undergone with many conceptual framework, one of the most important and desirable concept of human development which gained currency after the year nineteen ninety. Thus the present paper illustrates the indicator of Human development. The present paper also explains the report of human development composite by the UN. Present paper is trying to explain main factors included in the composition of human development report. Now every nation's economic development has measured by their human development. Now the HDI (Human Development Index) is an alternative measure that takes into account social and cultural growth alone. So the present paper explains the how economic development and human development interrelated with each other.

Keywords: Human development, Economic development, Index, Longevity, Gross enrollment ratio etc.

Introduction:

The study of development is not a new. Aristotle (384- 322 BC) argued that "Wealth is evidently not the good we are seeking, for it is merely useful and for the sake of something else." Another thinker Immanuel Kant (1724 - 1804) also explained, human beings as the real end of all activities, he observed so act as to treat humanity, whether in their own person or in that of any other, in every case as an end with all, never as means only. And Adam Smith (1723-1796), explained that economic development should enable a person to mix freely with other without being "ashamed to appear in public. A similar thought has introduced by the modern economics through, including Robert Mathus, Karl Mark and John Stuart Mill. There has remarkable shift in development economic after the 1960. Development economists try to explain why standards of living grow faster in some places than in others. There has an investigation what promotes economic development and what hindered it. The thinking of economist has started about what does and does not help countries to develop in the past several decades.

A clear trend that has emerged in the past few decades is the movement away from narrow measures of standards of living as indicators of development and towards broader more comprehensive indicators of quality of life. Most of the economists are agree that economic development should mean an improvement in people's quality of life. Income per person is a

good indicator of quality of life. Higher incomes allow people to do more of the activities that matter to them but there have some aspects of quality of life that are not clearly linked to incomes because of the some limitation of income as an indicator of quality of life ,overtime economist have expanded the range of measurements used to access economic development. The most successful attempt at broadening the definition of economic development and recognizing the subjectively of quality of life has come from the idea of "Human development" Mahbub- Ul- Haq a leading Pakistani economist, helped pioneer the concept while working at the United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) and was responsible for starting the human development report, which is now published annually by the U.N.

Objectives of the Study:

- i) To understand the concept of Economic Development.
- ii) To explain the concept of Human Development.
- iii) To illustrate the indicator of Human Development.
- iv) To find out the interrelation between Economic Development and Human Development.

Hypotheses:

- i) The concept of economic development depends on human welfare.

- ii) The human development is the main concept which included to measure economic development.

Research Methodology:

The present paper has developed by using the secondary sources. The published books journals, newspapers, articles, government reports, online databases and views of writers are used for this study.

Subject Analysis:

Economists have debate on the many different approaches to measuring economic development and human development. The well known Indian Nobel Prize winner economist Amartya Sen written that development is the expansion of the capabilities of people to lead the kind of life they have reason to Cherish. It means people wants more fulfilling life .The principal goal of development policy to create sustainable improvements in the quality of life for all people. It means raising per capita incomes and consumption is part of the goal, there has other objectives such as reducing poverty, expand access to health services, and increasing educational level are also important. Meeting these goals requires a comprehensive approach to development. The Idea of development has multiple goals.

The traditional development thinking has fail to meeting the comprehensives and lesions included in the new thinking of development. It emphasizes the need to reach beyond economic s to address societal issues in a holistic manner .The new perspectives come across with new visions such as equality, Education, Health, the environment, culture and social well being. The human development concept analyzes the new approach of economic development which included societal issue.

i) The concept of human development:

The UNDP Human Development Report was established in 1990 which has developed by the influential work of Amartya Sen ,Mehboob –Ul- haq, Richard Jolly, francs Steward and Meghanand Desai at the UNDP (United Nation Development Programme) They provided new frame work known as ‘human Development ‘embraces the enlargement of all human choices, many human choices extend far beyond economic well being ,knowledge ,health a clean physical environment ,political freedom and simple pleasures of life are not exclusively or largely dependent on income ,national wealth can expand peoples choices in

these areas but it might not The use that people make of their wealth, not the wealth itself , is decisive and unless societies recognize that their real wealth is their people ,an excessive obsession with material wealth can obscure the goal of enriching human lives.Thus the conceptually human development is the combination of people’s entitlements and actual attainments in the crucial aspects of their lives such as education, health and livelihood, taken together, these three elements, the sum of outcomes relating to schooling, health services and quality of life chances such as life expectancy and nutrition and importantly income. Human development has been defined as the “Process of enlarging people’s choices.” The Human development explain that one has to lead a long and healthy life and in the process to be educated and to enjoy life and in the process to be educated and to enjoy a decent standard of living. Also there have additional choices include political freedom, guaranteed human rights and self respect. To achieve such type of choices public policy play a vital role. Thus Human development report has a composite of the measurement of indicators which has followed by the government by the public policy .Public policy must be developed by the government agency which has depended on greater link between economic growth and human choice.

The government should design the policy in which the land reform, progressive tax services to reach all of the deprived population the removal of barriers to the entry of people in economic and political spheres and the equalization of their access to opportunities and the establishment of temporary social safety nets for those who may be bypassed by the markets or public policy actions. Such policy packages are fairly fundamental and will vary from one country to another but some features are common to all of them.

i) Development is analyzed and understood in terms of people participate in it or benefit from it the touchstone of the success of development policies becomes the betterment of people’s lives ,not just the expansion of production process.

ii) Human development is assumed to have two sides one is the formation of human capabilities such as improved health, knowledge and skills, the other is the use people make of their acquired capabilities for employment, productive activities, political affairs or leisure’s society needs to built up human capabilities as well as ensure equitable access to human opportunities considerable human

frustration results if the scales of human development do not finally balance the two sides.

iii) There is need to make a careful distinction is maintained between ends and means people are regarded as the ends but means are not forgotten. The expansion of GNP becomes an essential means for expanding many human options but the character and distribution of economic growth are measured against the yardstick of enriching the lives of people production processes are not treated in an abstract vacuum They acquire a human context.

iv) The human development analysis political cultural and social factors given as much attention as the economic factors. The study of the link between the economic and non economic environment is one of the most fascinating and rewarding aspect of this analysis.

v) This human development aspect explains that people are both the means and the ends of developments but people are not regarded as mere instruments for producing commodities through an augmentation of "human capital" The aspect needs to gives attention that it is always remembered that human beings are the ultimate end of development not convenient fodder for the materialistic machine.

Thus the human development has concerned not only with using these human capabilities (through investment in people) but also with using these human capabilities fully (through an enabling framework for growth and employment). Human development has four essential pillars equality, sustainability, productivity and empowerment.

ii) Measuring the human development:-

When one has measure the national development it is easier because it measures by the national income but when we measure the human development, there is a need for different indicator which would cover both social and economical aspects of people. Human development index is based on social and economic aspects. The GDP or income is a most predominant one in obtaining valued outcome in the course of development on the other hand the human development indicators are most appropriate in capturing desirable 'outcomes' for which the means are ultimately engaged in the process of development.

iii) Human Development index:-

Human Development index (HDI) focuses on three measurable dimensions of human development living a long and healthy life being educated and having a decent standard of life.

Thus it combines measures of longevity as measured by life expectancy at birth, education attainment as measured by a combination of adult literacy (2/3 weight age) and combined primary, secondary and Tertiary enrollment ratios (1/3 weight ages) and standard of living as measured by real GDP per capita (PPP\$) it allows a better and broader view of a countries development than does income alone.

For the construction of the index fixed minimum and maximum values have been established for each indicator of human development index.

1. Life expectancy at birth: 25 years and 85 years.
2. Adult literacy: 0% and 100%
3. Combined gross enrolment ratio: 0% and 100%
4. Real GDP per capita (PPP\$): \$100 and \$40000

The performance of each dimension is expressed as a value between 0 and 1 by applying a general formula.

Dimension index: $\frac{\text{Actual value} - \text{Minimum value}}{\text{Maximum value} - \text{minimum value}}$.

The HDI is a simple average of the life expectancy index, educational attainment index and adjusted real GDP per capita (PPP\$) Index and so it is derived by dividing the sum of the three indices by 3.

$\text{HDI} = \frac{1}{3} (\text{Life expectancy index}) + \frac{1}{3} (\text{Education index}) + \frac{1}{3} (\text{GDP index})$

The countries are ranked according to their HDI value. The performance is expressed between the value of 0 and 1. Thus the countries with 0.800 and above HDI value are considered as high HDI countries. Countries having HDI value between 0.500 – 0.799 are considered as medium HDI countries and countries having below 0.500 HDI value are considered as low HDI countries.

After the Second World War, development economics emerged as a distinct field of study. The HDRs (Human development Reports) have stimulated discussion world-wide leading, what now is called human development. Which include international and national government, policy makers, planners, opinion of leaders, parliamentarians, media, NGOs and various discussions of members of the civil society?

Relationship between economic development and human development:

The concept of development human development is an evolving one to previous development concept which considered that investing in improving human capabilities to contribute to economic development. Human development is the knowledge, skills, capabilities, attributes and

varies characteristics they possess. It is a set of skills, capabilities and experiences that the individual acquires and enables him to participate in economic life and gain income, which can improved through investment in education, health care, training and other forms of human capital.

The relationship between human development and economic development is a two way relationship, as each of them is reflected negatively and positively on the other that economic growth takes through improving human capabilities and achieving desired growth reflected in human development as it expands options in front of human resources in particular for individuals in general.

The human development is a social, economic and political process by its nature and human beings are its object and tools, and at the same time, its objective. The human development is the main objective of every development policy. To obtain economic development the human development is the most and prior condition of all process of development. The human development and economic development is interrelated with each other for country's overall development.

Conclusion:

The process of enlarging people's choices is known as human development. It has explain with people must be at the center of development process. It has argued that the development has to be woven around the people not people around the development. Now development concept has been shifted to quantitative factors to qualitative factors .The economic development is depend on well-being of people which reflects in human development. The ultimate aim of every country's development strategy is to improve the quality of life of country's people. There has clear trend emerged in the past few decades away from narrow measures of standard of living as indicator of development towards broader and more comprehensive indicator of quality of life. Most of the economists and readers are agree that economic development should mean an improvement in people's quality of life. Human development emerges as an important approach to development. Economic development now a day's widely explained that higher GNP growth, the expansion of output and wealth are only a means to development, the end of development is expansion of human capabilities. Human beings are the in the heart of any pace of development of society. The economic development and human

development is strongly interrelating with each other, without human development any country cannot fulfill economic development.

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